

EXPERIENCED TEACHERS AS SUPPORTERS IN CLASSROOM OBSERVATION AND FEEDBACK

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<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8081297>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 18th June 2023

Accepted: 25th June 2023

Online: 26th June 2023

KEY WORDS

Peer coaching, peer observation, feedback, professional development, reflection.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the role of peer coaching as one of the most valuable aspects of investigation. There are various observation and feedback conceptions introduced by several scientists. These correctly proposed observation techniques provide a path for educationalists for growing professionally.

Experienced teachers are recognized as knowledgeable who have much more experience in teaching. Teachers feel awkward if they are observed by experienced teachers as if the observer is there to punish the observee. It is undeniable fact that observing classroom has had a bad reputation (opinion about someone on how much respect or admiration he/she receives) in teaching because of its subjective, judgmental, and impressionistic (general) nature. Many teachers feel resentful by being observed by 'important people' or experienced teachers who judge their performance according to their own, not necessarily appropriate criteria, and make unwelcome 'suggestions' for change. It seems as if these observers come to observe whether observees' work is good or bad, right or wrong. Hence there will be strong resistance to observation among some teachers, precisely when teachers' are observed by master teachers.

Understanding experienced teachers' role as an educational leader in teaching and learning is mostly a neglected area, because a great number of teachers feel fearful when teachers observe the lesson, the reason can be various. May be most of the head teachers perform managerial and administrative roles, and it seems they are not going to observe and improve teaching instead to find fault of teaching as a manager of the staff. Experienced teachers are usually the ones who have been in the classroom for years and years; therefore, mostly for novice teachers it is nagging sense of anxiety and stressful experience to be observed. However, it is not quite opposite, that is, those teachers who are experienced professionally can share with their knowledge, easy ways of dealing with teaching boundaries, tested approaches and methods that work well when teaching students of different ages and styles. The most important thing that is required from novice and inexperienced teachers, or those who are not comfortable having an observer in the classroom should work on reflection- thorough analysis of self - behavior while teaching.

As Ghaye, T. claims, “reflection is a catalyst (condition that cause important change) for learning and a response to learning”. Moreover, Daudelin, M maintains that “reflection is a highly cognitive process. When a person engages in reflection, he or she takes an experience, and filters it through personal biases” [Post-observation feedback as an instigator of learning and change: Exploring the effect of feedback through student teachers’ self-reports; NurKurtoglu-Hooton Doctor of Philosophy, p. 23-24]

Roberts, J. points out that “reflection is, therefore, a crucial link between experience and learning; it is the means through which both concrete experience and abstract theory are transformed into knowledge” [Post-observation feedback as an instigator of learning and change: Exploring the effect of feedback through student teachers’ self-reports; NurKurtoglu-Hooton Doctor of Philosophy, p. 26]

An experienced teacher acts as an educational leader by giving professional support to teachers, creating close relationships with the other teachers and by creating a collaborative learning environment at educational establishments. As a mentee he/she gives advice, help other teachers for a particular work over a period of time.

The study was conducted with two teachers as research participants, having an average of ten years of teaching experience. We chose two teachers one of them Mamirbaeva, D. works as a Head of English Philology Department in Nukus State University and Tadjieva, A. are recognized as experienced teachers.

The findings suggest that experienced teachers perceived his/her role as that of a facilitator, team builder and change agent, mentee, supervisor also acted as an instructional leader and a manager.

As we have accentuated about peer observation in our previews part, in this section we are going to refer primarily to this kind of observation i.e. peer observation.

Broyce, B. and Showers, B first introduced the notion of peer coaching in 1981, as a powerful educational strategy for improving and refining the quality of teaching. Even though peer coaching is widely used among the instructors in developed countries, it still remains less used particularly in our country and exactly in our university as well.

Above mentioned scientists refer peer observation as peer coaching; further we also would like to talk about peer observation as peer coaching.

Peer coaching is a form of institutional educators` development that provides a chance to reduce the teachers’ obstacles, weaknesses and improve teacher effectiveness. Peer coaching helps teachers to expand their repertoire of teaching styles, strategies and behaviors. The inquiry engages English teachers who have been practicing peer coaching in English Philology Department of Karakalpak State University. Most of the teachers are novice teachers of this faculty and who were eager to heighten their professional growth. After the peer coaching teachers expressed their impressions about the process, benefits of peer coaching and experience they got in peer coaching by giving informal interview. Moreover, teachers pointed out their intentional changes of those issues that teachers faced while doing peer coaching.

The main enlightening quality of peer coaching is that you can exchange any kind of limitations of your teaching with your teacher corresponding.

Overall, findings of the study demonstrated that teachers had utilized only observation and visited each other's classrooms where they identified strengths and weaknesses in their teaching practices. Teachers' mutual lesson observations provided them the chance to learn new teaching methods, strategies and activities. In post-observational discussions they were involved in problem-solving activities, lesson structure, classroom management strategies and student involvement, student interaction and issues related to types of teaching activities, and of course weak points to be improved, they had their own evaluators whom they could exchange everything related to teaching without embarrassment.

From the study you can see that peer coaching activities are exchanging some valuable experience, sharing ideas with the person/teacher whom you want to work with in order to find something important for your own teaching. The study draws great attention to teachers' professional knowledge, growth and excellent teaching experiences with the help of conducting of peer coaching activities.

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